

SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF CREATIVITY

Zoir Botirov

Teacher of the Termiz State University

E-mail: botirovzoirbek3@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the study of creativity in adolescents and its individual characteristics, the formation of creativity in adolescents, strategies that develop creativity, and the socio-psychological basis of creativity.

Key words: *Creativity, intellectual development, neuropsychological assessment, cognitive, talent, motivation.*

Of creativity include various factors affecting the development and manifestation of creativity. These factors can be broadly divided into individual characteristics, social influences and environmental conditions. Creativity is deeply connected with social conditions in various ways:

1. Social influences on creativity:

-Cultural values and norms: Social values and expectations can shape how creativity is perceived and valued. Cultures that emphasize conformity and tradition may inhibit creative expression, while cultures that embrace innovation and risk-taking may foster creativity.

-Exposure to different perspectives: Exposure to different cultures, viewpoints, and experiences can broaden a person's worldview and stimulate creative thinking. Cross-cultural interactions and exposure to different art forms can generate new ideas and approaches.

2. Social impact of creativity:

can foster social progress and innovation by challenging norms, proposing new solutions, and inspiring others. Creative individuals are catalysts for social change and can contribute to the development of new technologies, artistic expressions, and social structures.

-Social cohesion and identity: Creative expression can support social cohesion and strengthen community bonds by presenting shared experiences, promoting understanding and celebrating cultural diversity. Artistic traditions, festivals and community art projects can bring people together and foster a sense of belonging.

-Social problem solving and conflict resolution: Creativity can be used to solve social problems, develop effective solutions, and help resolve conflicts. Creative approaches to social issues such as education, health care, and environmental sustainability can lead to positive social change.

3. Social conditions and creative expression:

-Economic conditions: access to resources, education, and opportunities can significantly influence creative expression. Economic disparities can hinder the development of creative potential by limiting access to creative tools, training and platforms.

-Political freedom and freedom of speech: freedom of speech, expression, and assembly are essential to the development of creativity. A political environment that stifles dissent and limits creative expression can stifle innovation and cultural progress.

-Technological advances: Technological advances provide new tools and platforms for creative expression, expand creative opportunities, and allow for greater distribution of creative works. However, technology can create distractions, limit personal interactions, and potentially homogenize creative output.

So, the relationship between creativity and social conditions is complex and multifaceted. Creativity is influenced by social factors and it in turn influences society. Understanding these connections is critical to fostering creativity in individuals, promoting social progress, and building a more creative and innovative society.

There are some scientific theories about the interaction between creativity and sociality:

-Social constructivist view: This view emphasizes the role of social interaction and cooperation in the formation of creative ideas. This suggests that creativity is not just an individual phenomenon, but a product of social processes in which people exchange ideas, build on each other's contributions, and clarify concepts through collective discourse.

-Social cognitive view: This view focuses on how social factors influence the cognitive processes that contribute to creativity. It suggests that social interactions can enhance creativity by providing people with access to new information, different perspectives, and cognitive tools that help them solve problems and generate ideas.

-Social identity view: This view emphasizes the role of social identity and belonging in stimulating creative expression. This suggests that people are more likely to engage in creative endeavors when they feel connected to a supportive community that values and encourages creativity.

-Social-ecological view: This view emphasizes the interaction of individual, social and environmental factors in shaping creative development. This suggests that creativity is not confined to individuals or social groups, but emerges from the dynamic

interaction between individuals, their social environment, and the wider cultural and environmental context.¹

These theories provide valuable insights into the complex interplay between creativity and sociality. They emphasize the importance of social interactions, collaboration, and cultural contexts in shaping creative development and expression. Understanding these connections is essential for developing creativity in individuals and developing a more creative and innovative society.

Social and psychological factors play a major role in creativity. These factors can affect a person's creative potential, motivation, and ability to express their creativity. Adolescent years are crucial for the development of creativity. In this period, adolescents develop a sense of self-awareness and become more and more independent. They also form new relationships and explore new interests. All of these experiences can help foster creativity. Creativity is a powerful skill that can be developed by anyone. By cultivating creativity, we can positively impact ourselves, our communities, and the world. It is the ability to generate new ideas and solve problems in innovative ways. Creativity is necessary to ensure economic growth, social development and cultural richness. Here are some reasons why creativity is a necessary skill:

-Creativity develops cooperation. Creative people can often see new connections and opportunities that others miss. This creative thinking ability helps to develop cooperation and teamwork.

-Creativity increases well-being. Creativity can be a source of great joy and satisfaction. It helps us express ourselves, connect with others, and make a positive impact on the world.

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